

IPBES VA Chapter 3 - Reviews on IPLC approaches to valuation

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Objective/Justification: This review corresponds to the IPBES Values assessment Chapter 3. The methodology explained in this report responds to the mandate of Ch. 3 to assess different valuation methodologies and approaches, including (a) biophysical, social and cultural, economic, health and holistic (including indigenous and local community-based) and (b) approaches for the integration of different types of values. In order to provide evidence to present the state of the art on valuation methods used by the IPLC, three different reviews were conducted.

Process overview:

Review of ILK dialogue reports and other IPBES resources on ILK

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Review of literature on Indigenous Knowledge

miro

Indigenous and hybrid methodologies

Protocol

Review of ILK dialogue reports and other IPBES resources on ILK

In order to provide a review of the state of the art on valuation methods, in particular regarding non-academic reports and publications (previous IPBES Assessments, previous assessments of valuation methods), a review was performed, regarding previous IPBES efforts in particular IPBES Assessments Dialogues and other IPBES resources on ILK:

Protocol:

Type of analysis/search/review: Review of ILK dialogue reports and other IPBES resources on ILK.

Search languages: English

Search engine: IPBES

Exact search date: January 15, 2020

Sample extracted (A1): (13+1)= 14 dialogues and a report

Fields extracted:

- Author
- Title
- Year
- Editors
- Publisher

Location and Format of the Data: NA

Search terms:

Two search criteria were used
a) Reports of ALL the ILK DIALOGUES that accompanied the development of previous IPBES Assessments,
b) Other IPBES resources on ILK

Treatment applied (R1): Reports were scoped in and out based on their reference to valuation or research methods.

Sample extracted (A2): (8+1)=9 dialogues and a report.

Location and Format of the Data (A2): IPBES_VA_3.5_Dialogues and others review_(A2).csv

Analysis of the data: The documents selected were read and used to summarise the main findings regarding the integration of indigenous worldviews in IPBES dialogues and other publications.

Review of literature on Indigenous Knowledge

In order to provide a review of the state of the art on valuation methods, in particular regarding the indigenous communities, a review on documents, related to ILK, from UNESCO was performed.

Protocol:

Type of analysis/search/review: Search on UNESCO collection using Zotero.

Search languages: English & Spanish

Search engine: UNESCO database

Exact search date: May 1st - November 30, 2020

Sample extracted (B1): 500 documents

Fields extracted:

- Author
- Title
- Year
- Abstract
- Publication title
- DOI

Location and Format of the Data: NA

Search terms:

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TS=("Indigenous Local Knowledge")
TS=("Indigenous stewardship")
TS=("Indigenous values")
TS=("Indigenous Knowledge")
TS=("Indigenous stewardship")
TS=("Indigenous values")
TS=("Indigenous People and Local Communities valuing nature")
TS=("Valuation")
TS=("Valuation Modification")
TS=("Valuation Conservation")
TS=("Contingent valuation")
TS=("Biocultural values")
TS=("Cultural values")
TS=("Development")
TS=("Environmental impact")
TS=("Development project")
TS=("Extractive project")
TS=("Extraction")
TS=("Decision making")
TS=("Values of Nature")
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TS=(valuation of nature)
TS=(Evaluation)
TS=(Indigenous)
TS=(Indigenous fire management)
TS=(Indigenous fisheries)
TS=(Indigenous forest management)
TS=(Indigenous knowledge systems)
TS=(Indigenous land and sea management)
TS=(Indigenous land management)
TS=(Indigenous lands)
TS=(Indigenous landscape burning)
TS=(Indigenous landscape management)
TS=(Indigenous livelihoods)
TS=(Indigenous management)
TS=(Indigenous meteorology)
TS=(Indigenous movement)
TS=(Indigenous participation)
TS=(Indigenous peoples)
TS=(Indigenous peoples Zimbabwe)
TS=(Indigenous peoples and communities)
TS=(Indigenous peoples and Dmas)
TS=(Indigenous peoples keywords)
TS=(Indigenous rights)
TS=(Indigenous water rights)
TS=(Indigenous water values)
TS=(Indigenous weather forecasting)
TS=(Indigenous rights á regional)
TS=(Indigenous stewardships)
TS=(Indigenous subsistence use)
TS=(Indigenous systems)
TS=(Indigenous Technical Knowledge)
TS=(Indigenous territories)
TS=(Indigenous tourism)
TS=(Indigenous well-being)
TS=(Indigenous wisdom)
TS=(Indigenous worldviews)
TS=(Indigenous mining interface)
TS=(Indigenous knowledge)
TS=(Indigenousness)
TS=(UN Declaration)

Treatment applied (R1): Reports were scoped in and out based on their reference to valuation or research methods used by indigenous people.

Sample extracted (B2): 92 papers

Location and Format of the Data (B2): IPBES_VA_3.5_ILK review_(B2).csv

Analysis of the data: Documents were reviewed and used to summarise the findings on the state of the art of the valuation methods used by the indigenous communities, this evidence is presented in different sections across Chapter 3, in particular in section 3.2.4 Valuation Practice in IPLC contexts.

Indigenous and hybrid methodologies

A review was performed focused on consolidating worldwide initiatives to develop IPLC methodologies, the epistemological roots of the new methodologies and to identify which initiatives are particularly relevant for valuation. Papers presented here were selected through expert knowledge.

Protocol:

Type of analysis/search/review: Expert knowledge

Search languages: English

Exact Search Date: December 1, 2020

Sample extracted (C): 110 papers

Fields extracted:

- Author
- Title
- Year
- Publication

Location and Format of the Data (C): IPBES_VA_3.5 Indigenous and hybrid methods_ (C).docx

Analysis of the Data: Papers were screened and read to summarise the state of the art of the worldwide initiatives to develop IPLC methodologies, in Section 3.2.4 Valuation Practice in IPLC contexts, across Chapter 3 and in the Annexes.

Documents attached:

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_VA_3.5 Dialogues and others review_(A2)	.xlsx	11 KB	Selected IPBES documents (9 documents)
B	IPBES_VA_3.5_ILK review_(B2).csv	.csv	153 KB	Selected documents from the UNESCO database (92 documents)
C	IPBES_VA_3.5 Indigenous and hybrid methods_ (C)	.docx	28 KB	List of papers selected through expert knowledge (110 papers)